

Synthesis of Some New 2-Aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones and Their Related Compounds as Potential Pesticides

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Manuscript received 3 January 1980; revised 3 June 1980, accepted 26 July 1980

2-aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (II) obtained by cyclisation of N-aryloxyacetyl ureas (I) with Br_2/NaOH were treated with aryloxyacetyl chloride, and NH_4SCN /benzoyl chloride to yield 4-aryloxyacetyl-2-aryloxy methyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (III) and 2-aryloxymethyl-4-(N-benzoylthioamido)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (IV), respectively. The 1,3,4-oxadiazolinone (II) on treatment with $\text{NH}_4\text{OH}/\text{CS}_2$ yielded 2-aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-4-dithiocarboxylic acids (V), which when refluxed with I_2/EtOH afforded bis (2-aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-4-thiocarbonyl)disulphides (VI). Out of thirteen screened compounds, two exhibited herbicidal activity in the range of 2,4-D (sodium salt), a commercial herbicide, against *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*, and three showed fungitoxicity of the order of Dithane M-45 (Manganous ethylenebisdithiocarbamate with zinc ion), a commercial fungicide, against *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

THE novel exploration of *oxadiazon* (G-315), the 2-*tert*-butyl-4-(2, 4-dichloro-5-*iso*-propoxyphenyl)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-one (1) which is a broad spectrum commercial herbicide recommended for application on various crops and ornamental plants, has been an incentive for investigations in the field of 1,3,4-oxadiazole herbicides. Further, various phenolic ethers¹⁻⁴, 2-substituted- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-5-ones⁵⁻⁹, amides¹⁰ and thioureas¹¹⁻¹³ have been reported as useful biologically active compounds especially as herbicides and fungicides.

In view of above, it was speculated that the combination of *oxadiazon* with the moieties responsible for biological activity might result in compounds with better performance.

In addition to the fact that a number of heteroaryl disulphides have been reported as useful bactericides, fungicides, acaricides and herbicides, one might expect that the disulphides with biologically versatile 1,3,4-oxadiazole nucleus would be compounds of high potency.

Considering these facts in view, the title compounds have been synthesised to study their herbicidal and fungicidal activities.

The title compounds have been synthesised according to the scheme 1.

The 2-aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones(II) prepared by cyclisation²³ of N-aryloxyacetylureas (0.1M) with an ice-cold solution of Br_2/NaOH (2N) in 80-85% yield were stirred with aryloxyacetyl chloride for 30 min in an ice bath followed by washing with Na_2CO_3 solution to yield 4-aryloxyacetyl-2-aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (III) in 85-89% yield. The 2-aryloxymethyl-4-(N-benzoylthioamido)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (IV) with 90-95% yield, were prepared according to the method of Doughlass and Dains²⁴ by refluxing (II) with NH_4SCN /benzoyl chloride in acetone for 2 hr. (V) were prepared in good yield (81-85%) by stirring a mixture of (II) 0.05M, Ammonia solution (sp.gr. 0.88) and CS_2 for 2 hr at

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room temperature followed by acidification with dil. HCl, which on refluxing with I_2 /EtOH, furnished bis (2-aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-4-thio-carbonyl) disulphides (VI) in 90-95% yield. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses, ir and NMR spectra.

Thirteen of the title compounds have been screened for their herbicidal activity against the weeds *Argemone mexicana*¹⁹ and *Cyperus rotundus*¹⁹ and fungi *Aspergillus niger*²⁰ and *Helminthosporium oryzae*²¹. The results obtained have been compared with 2,4-D, a commercial herbicide and *Dithane M-45*, a commercial fungicide which were tested under the similar conditions. Out of the thirteen tested compounds, two exhibited herbicidal activity in the range of 2,4-D and three showed fungitoxicity of the order *Dithane M-45* at concentrations 1000 ppm and 100 ppm. However, the bis-oxo-oxadiazolinthiocarbonyl disulphides (VI) were found to be more active than 4-aryloxyacetyl-, and 4-(N-benzoylthiomido)- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (III), (IV).

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (in KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer (model 521) and NMR on 60 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. The chemical shifts are reported in τ (ppm) values.

N-aryloxyacetylureas (I) were prepared by the method of Pearl and Dehn²².

2-Aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-5-ones(II)²³ : I (0.1M) was added portionwise with stirring to an ice-cold solution of NaOH (2M, 168 ml) and bromine (17.6g). The mixture was poured into water after 15 min to yield the oxadiazolinone (II) which were recrystallised from ethanol, and are recorded in Table 1A.

TABLE 1A—2-ARYLOXYMETHYL- Δ^2 -1,3,4-OXADIAZOLIN-5-ONES(II)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
1 ^a	H	164	85
2 ^b	<i>o</i> -Cl	165-166	80
3	<i>p</i> -Cl	199-201	82
4	2,4-Dichloro	160	75
5	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	169	76

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in KBr)

	C=N	C-O-C	*C=O	N-H	Substituted benzene nucleus
a	1615	1260,1040	1715	3440,3140	1500,770,710
b	1615	1020,1250	1710	3440,3160	1510,1470,730

*The cyclic C=O band (1710-1715 cm⁻¹) was present in the compounds (II), confirming their existence as mainly in the oxo form instead of the tautomeric hydroxy form (IIa).

TABLE 1B—4-ARYLOXYACETYL-2-ARYLOXYMETHYL- Δ^2 -1,3,4-OXADIAZOLIN-5-ONES (III)

S.No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %
6	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	173-174	81
7	H	2,4-Dichloro	156	89
8	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	163	74
9 ^a	<i>o</i> -Cl	2,4-Dichloro	99-101	85
10	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	158	80
11	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	160-161	70
12	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	184-185	72
13	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	138	84
14	<i>p</i> -Cl	2,4-Dichloro	180	86
15	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	162	87
16	2,4-Dichloro	2,4-Dichloro	105-107	73
17	2,4-Dichloro	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	169	74
18	2,4-Dichloro	<i>p</i> -Cl	186	76
19	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	170-171	79
20	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	2,4-Dichloro	176	68

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir Spectra (in KBr)

	C=N	C=O (Cyclic)	C=O (Acyclic)	C-O-C	Substituted benzene nucleus
a	1615	1715	1630	1040 1260	1490, 880, 800, 760
b	1630	1720	1640	1030 1260	1500, 1450, 880, 820

TABLE 1C—2-ARYLOXYMETHYL-4-(N-BENZOYLTHIOAMIDO)- Δ^2 -1,3,4 OXADIAZOLIN-5-ONES (IV)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
21	H	155	85
22	<i>o</i> -Cl	133	88
23	<i>p</i> -Cl	160	90
24 ^a	2,4-Dichloro	141	92
25	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	159	95

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in Nujol mull)

C=N	C-O-C	C=O (Cyclic)	C=O (Acyclic)	C=S	N-H	Substituted benzene nucleus
a 1630	1050, 1260	1740	1700	1220	3300	1560, 1485, 3070, 805, 730

NMR spectrum in DMSO-d₆ (60 MHz)

Protons	Chemical shift (τ)	Multiplicity
a Aromatic (8H)	1.9-2.5	Complex multiplet
-OCH ₃ (2H)	5.1	Singlet
-NH (H)	6.6	Singlet

TABLE 1D—2-ARYLOXYMETHYL-5-OXO- Δ^2 -1,3,4-OXADIAZOLIN-4-DITHIOCARBOXYLIC ACIDS

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
26	H	180-182	80
27	<i>o</i> -Cl	230	82
28	<i>p</i> -Cl	215	95
29	2,4-Dichloro	195-198	76
30 ^a	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	130-135	80

BIS (2-ARYLOXYMETHYL-5-OXO- Δ^2 -1,3,4-OXADIAZOLIN-4-THIOCARBONYL) DISULPHIDES

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
31	H	232-235	75
32	<i>o</i> -Cl	200	80
33	<i>p</i> -Cl	185	90
34	2,4-Dichloro	172-175	95
35 ^b	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	220-225	95

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in KBr)

C=N	C=O	C-O-C	C=S	S-H	Substituted benzene nucleus
a 1622	1730	1040, 1260	1120	2560	1520, 780, 700
b 1650	1260, 1045	1710	1210	—	1580, 1500, 800, 680

C, H and N analysis of compound given in Table 1A and 1B and N, S, analysis of compound given in Table 1C and 1D are consistent.

4-Aryloxyacetyl-2-aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4 oxadiazolin-5-ones(III): A mixture of oxadiazolinone (II, 0.02 M) and aryloxyacetyl chloride (0.02 M) was stirred for about 30 min in an ice-bath and then cold water was added. The product thus precipitated was filtered, washed several times with Na₂CO₃ solution and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds (III) are recorded in Table 1B.

2-Aryloxymethyl-4 (N-benzoylthioamido)-1, 3, 4- Δ^2 -oxadiazolin-5-ones (IV)^{2,4}: Were prepared by reacting equimolar quantities of (II) NH₄SCN and benzoyl chloride in acetone following the method of Douglass and Dains^{2,4}. The compounds (IV) thus prepared were recrystallised from acetone-ethanol mixture, and are recorded in Table 1C.

2-Aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-4 dithiocarboxylic acids (V): To a mixture of 2-aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (II, 0.05M) and ammonia solution (15 ml, sp.gr. 0.88), CS₂ (0.005 M) was added dropwise. After stirring the reaction mixture for 2 hr. at room temperature it was acidified with dil. HCl to give the corresponding dithiocarboxylic acids which were recrystallised from aqueous-ethanol (20/80; v/v) as white crystals and are recorded in Table 1D.

Bis (2-aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4 oxadiazolin-4-thiocarbonyl) disulphides VI: To an ethanolic suspension of 2-aryloxymethyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-4-dithiocarboxylic acid (V), ethanolic solution of I₂ was added until no further decolorisation of I₂ was observed. The mixture was heated on water bath for 15 min, cooled and poured into water followed by basification with aq. ammonia to yield the disulphides (VI) which were recrystallised from ethanol and are recorded in Table 1D.

Herbicidal Screening

Herbicidal activity was evaluated by pre-emergence test at three concentrations viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm against *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*. The number of replications in each case was three. Seeds/tubers of the test plants were soaked for 24 hr. in the test solutions and then planted. 2,4-D (sodium salt) was also tested under similar conditions (with a view to comparing the results). The percentage inhibition by various compounds are recorded in Table 2.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{Gc - Gt}{Gc} \times 100$$

where, Gc = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in control.

Gt = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in test solution/suspension.

TABLE 2 - HERBICIDAL SCREENING

Compound serial as in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C and 1D	Average Percentage Inhibition					
	Weed- <i>A. mexicana</i> Concentrations used			Weed- <i>C. rotundus</i> Concentrations used		
	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm
1	60.5	33.2	24.4	53.6	21.6	13.5
3	62.7	35.7	26.1	56.8	23.0	14.9
4	66.0	37.3	28.2	68.4	36.9	18.3
5	64.7	35.9	26.5	65.3	25.6	16.5
6	68.4	39.0	31.5	68.1	39.4	26.6
7	71.5	40.1	34.0	69.4	31.3	29.7
13	66.1	39.4	28.1	60.3	30.4	20.8
14	95.4	56.9	27.2	94.8	56.2	28.2
21	96.3	58.5	28.4	95.7	57.3	28.9
24	97.9	61.1	30.4	96.4	58.5	30.1
31	72.5	40.2	15.5	55.1	41.4	19.7
33	63.4	37.0	27.7	58.2	25.2	16.8
34	85.2	48.3	22.8	79.5	40.6	18.9
2,4-D	100	84.2	66.7	100	82.6	61.5
(Sodium salt)						

TABLE 3 - FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound serial as in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C and 1D	Average Percentage Inhibition after 96 hours					
	Organism- <i>A. niger</i> Concentrations used			Organism- <i>H. oryzae</i> Concentrations used		
	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm
1	53.7	27.5	18.2	48.2	18.4	9.4
3	56.5	28.4	20.1	51.4	21.3	11.7
4	62.0	32.5	21.9	64.8	29.6	15.2
5	59.8	30.1	21.2	58.1	22.3	13.7
6	66.1	34.3	22.4	65.0	30.1	18.6
7	68.3	39.2	23.0	69.9	38.4	20.5
13	64.4	31.4	18.3	61.4	23.6	17.5
14	95.9	56.3	31.4	94.6	54.7	28.1
21	96.7	60.1	36.3	95.5	61.8	50.2
24	100	65.5	60.8	100	70.4	55.7
31	98.4	62.8	40.1	97.2	63.0	51.2
33	100	68.6	52.2	100	70.2	53.1
34	100	72.3	55.0	100	74.4	54.3
<i>Dithane M-45</i> (a commercial fungicide)	100	85.4	72.6	96.4	82.9	68.3

Fungicidal screening

The antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique²⁵ against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at 1000 ppm, 100 ppm and 10 ppm. The number of replications in each case was three. A commercial fungicide *Dithane M-45* was tested under similar conditions (with a view to comparing the results). The percentage inhibitions by various compounds are recorded in Table 3.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C-T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hours.

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hours.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the screening data (Tables 2 and 3) that all the screened compounds were toxic to weeds (*A. mexicana* and *C. rotundus*) and fungi (*A. niger* and *H. oryzae*) in varied degrees, but the order of their toxicities was not so encouraging as could be expected from the combination of phenolic ether, oxadiazolinone and thiourea moieties. The compound Nos. 14 and 24 had the activity of the order of 2,4-D (sodium salt) at 1000 ppm, presumably by virtue of possessing 2,4-dichlorophenoxy moiety which is common toxophore in the herbicides of 2,4-D family. The compound Nos. 24, 33 and 34 inhibited >50% the growth of both the fungi even at 10 ppm, and thus appear to be promising fungicides. The compound No. 34 (3) was most active against both the fungal species, and had fungitoxicity of the order *Dithane M-45* (Manganese ethylenebis-dithiocarbamate with zinc ion) even at 100 ppm, it is only due to the S-S bond fission almost identical to that of thiram (2), a commercial fungicide, involving this bond fission in its mode of action²⁶.

However, the thioamido compound Nos. 21 and 24 were more toxic to both the weeds than their parent compounds, No. 1 and 4 as well as 4-aryloxyacetyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones Nos. 5, 6 and 14 respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur, for providing departmental facilities and Dr A. K. Singh (U.S.A) for recording ir, NMR spectra and elemental analyses. One of the authors (B. K. B.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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